

Borse's Formula for Gravitational Interactions of Ordinary Matter and Dark Matter

Mst. Ishant. K. Borse
Shloka 105, Hari Sanskruti, Nashik
Road, Nashik, Maharashtra India - 422101
Email : ishant.kborse12@gmail.com

Abstract

In this paper, we delve into the intricate interplay between ordinary matter and dark matter, aiming to illuminate the elusive nature of dark matter and its profound effects on the cosmos. I introduce a novel formula that describes the gravitational interactions between ordinary matter and dark matter, providing a theoretical framework for understanding their dynamics. Through rigorous analysis and theoretical derivations, I elucidate the significance of this formula in shedding light on the mysteries surrounding dark matter and its implications for cosmology and astrophysics.

Introduction

The nature of dark matter has long captivated the imagination of physicists and astronomers alike. Despite comprising a significant portion of the universe's mass-energy content, dark matter remains elusive, revealing its presence only through gravitational effects on visible matter. In this paper, we embark on a journey to unravel the mysteries of dark matter, focusing on its gravitational interactions with ordinary matter. Central to my investigation is a newly proposed formula that encapsulates the gravitational force exerted by dark matter on a test particle in its vicinity. By elucidating the implications of this formula, we aim to deepen our understanding of dark matter and its role in shaping the cosmos.

Theoretical Framework

The formula under consideration, denoted as F_{DM} , describes the force due to dark matter acting on a test particle, m_{test} , in the presence of a dark matter density distribution, $\rho_{DM}(\mathbf{r})$. This formula is grounded in the principles of gravitational physics, incorporating Newton's law of universal gravitation within the framework of dark matter dynamics. The integral term represents the cumulative gravitational effect of dark matter density within the vicinity of the test particle, emphasizing the role of spatial distribution in shaping gravitational interactions.

The gravitational force F_{DM} exerted by dark matter on the test particle is given by:

$$F_{DM} = -G \cdot m_{test} \cdot \int \frac{\rho_{DM}(\mathbf{r})}{|\mathbf{r}|^2} \cdot \hat{\mathbf{r}} dV$$

Where:

1. **FDM**: This represents the force due to dark matter acting on the test particle. It's the quantity we're trying to calculate.
2. **G**: This is the gravitational constant, which appears in Newton's law of universal gravitation. It's a fundamental constant that relates the strength of the gravitational force to the masses of the objects and the distance between them.
3. m_{test} : This is the mass of the test particle experiencing the gravitational force.
 - **$\rho_{\text{DM}}(\mathbf{r})$** : This represents the density of dark matter at a given position $\mathbf{r}$ in space. It's a function that describes how dark matter is distributed in the region surrounding the test particle.
5. **$|\mathbf{r}|$** : This is the magnitude of the position vector $\mathbf{r}$, which represents the distance between the test particle and the element of dark matter at position $\mathbf{r}$.
6. **$\mathbf{r}$** : This is the position vector pointing from the dark matter element to the test particle. It indicates the direction of the gravitational force acting on the test particle due to the nearby dark matter.
7. **$\hat{\mathbf{r}}$** : This is the unit vector in the direction of $\mathbf{r}$, which is used to indicate the direction of the gravitational force.
8. **dV** : This represents an infinitesimal volume element surrounding the test particle. The integral is taken over the entire volume surrounding the test particle to sum up the contributions from all dark matter elements.
9. **$\int$** : represents an integral in mathematics, and it's called the integral sign. It's used to denote the operation of integration, which is essentially a way to find the accumulation of quantities over a continuous range.

The formula essentially integrates the gravitational force exerted by each element of dark matter in the vicinity of the test particle. The force experienced by the test particle is the sum of these contributions, taking into account the density of dark matter at each position and the distance between the test particle and each dark matter element.

This formula is a way to model the gravitational effects of dark matter, which is thought to make up a significant portion of the mass in the universe but does not interact electromagnetically and thus cannot be directly observed. By studying the gravitational influence of dark matter on visible matter, scientists can infer the presence and distribution of dark matter in the universe.

This formula captures the gravitational influence of dark matter on ordinary matter, providing insights into the dynamics of cosmic structures and the formation of galaxies and galaxy clusters.

Implication and Significance

The proposed formula offers a powerful tool for probing the nature of dark matter and its effects on the cosmos. By analysing the gravitational interactions between ordinary matter and dark matter, researchers can glean valuable information about the distribution, composition, and evolution of dark matter structures. Furthermore, this formula lays the groundwork for future observational and theoretical studies aimed at unravelling the mysteries of dark matter and advancing our understanding of the universe's underlying dynamics.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the formula describing the interactions between ordinary matter and dark matter represents a significant advancement in our quest to unravel the mysteries of the cosmos. Through its elucidation of gravitational dynamics, this formula offers valuable insights into the elusive nature of dark matter and its profound impact on the universe at large. As we continue to explore the frontiers of astrophysics and cosmology, the theoretical framework provided by this formula promises to guide our endeavours and deepen our understanding of the fundamental forces shaping the cosmos.

Reference :

- Newton's Law of universal gravitational.
- An Introduction to Particle Dark Matter by Stefano Profumo.
- Dark Matter and Dark Energy by Brian Clegg.
- The 4 Percent Universe by Richard Panek.
- Dark Cosmos in Search of Our Universes Missing Mass by Dan Hooper.
- Chapter 3- Vectors pdf by University of Central Florida.
- An Introduction to General Relativity Spacetime and Geometry by Sean. M. Carroll.
- Gravitation by Kip Thorne.
- General Relativity by Robert Wald.

- Relativity: The Special and the General Theory by Albert Einstein.
- The Geometry of Spacetime by James Callahan.
- Calculus by James Stewart.
- Special Issue : The Interaction of Dark Matter with Ordinary Matter displayed at website of MDPI.
- Dark Matter by CERN.
- Article displayed at JPL NASA website named as NASA Scientists Help Probe Dark Energy by Testing Gravity.
- Dark Matter by NASA Science.